

Measuring Satisfaction of Customers Regarding Islamic Financing of Meezan Bank Limited

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ABSTRACT

PURPOSE: *The purpose of this research paper is to examine analyzing and outlining the customer satisfaction level with regards to their perception about the Islamic banking system. The main purpose is to eliminate the problem related to banking industry and to determine its rights and duties to satisfy customers.*

DESIGN OR METHODOLOGY: *This paper is set out according to the principle instruments and designed for measuring the customer satisfaction for Islamic banking and its related bodies. The analysis of the Islamic system is basically organized on the basis of banking system for measuring customers towards Islamic banking system and its shariah complaint rules and regulations.*

FINDINGS: *All across the rights for customers is being considered as a lawful and constitutional concerned nationally and internationally. The findings also suggest the significance of customer rights and the conceptual frame work for measuring human rights effect the implementation. The paradiagm of this research and its rights are effectively translated into developed banking system for increasing Islamic industry for banking as a whole.*

RESULTS: *Primary data are collected through survey, questionnaire and observation and secondary data are collected through books , articles , research papers , journals , literature , published material , other sources , print media article collection , magazines , newspapers , published electronic services , e-journals , websites , weblogs , unpublished general records , government records health education and census data , public and private sector records and retrospective information.*

CONCLUSION: *In short the conclusion is that the wave of market economy downturn has a greater strength into its own self financially and the research study proofs that conducting the research study is crucial and beneficial towards the societal developmental factors like customer satisfying measurements.*

LIMITATIONS FOR RESEARCH:

The required research is not enough for the measuring the customer satisfaction as a whole or specifically the example of effectiveness about the rights of customers and their satisfaction regarding Islamic banking system

KEYWORDS: *Customer, Satisfaction, Rights, Banking*

1-INTRODUCTION:

1.1-PREAMBLE:

The first leading Islamic bank in the history of Pakistan that signs the memorandum of association with the journal of Islamic banking and finance (JIBF) which is the largest and the oldest research publication of Pakistan.

Meezan bank wants to fill the gap between academia and the industry. The largest research team across the entire banking sector in Pakistani banking industry that shares the research papers, articles and case studies of real world scenarios in Islamic banking industry.

The statement of point is the agreement was duly signed by meson banks head of the consumer banking and marketing. Head related to shariah compliance ordinance mention bank focuses over the vision for establishing Islamic banking organization which is the first choice and initiative in an Islamic sector for the cause of development of the Islamic industry.

Capacities of Islamic Bank Business Association is fundamentally begun for the purpose of benefit by performing legal exercises. Banks are additionally one of the business associations that give a set of items also administrations to produce benefits. Beginning of Islamic keeping money polishes in Pakistan made different dangers and chances to live up to clients' desires by the procurement of value administrations. It launched a solid rivalry for Islamic banks to rival their

associates and customary banks for more amazing benefits. It was watched that the managing an account industry accomplished firm rivalry with banks and with other monetary establishments to pull in potential clients (Hull, 2002).

1.2-PAKISTAN ISLAMIC BANK OVERVIEW:

Currently 5 fully fledged Islamic Banks with 725 branches and 13 conventional banks with 372 Islamic branches operating in the country.

Meezan Bank Limited was the first to get license of Islamic Banking. The bank has shown growth in just 10 years. The Bank business growth termed as Fastest Growing Islamic Bank in Pakistan. With a networking of 310 branches in 90 cities across Pakistan and it is the largest Islamic bank in Pakistan.

Islamic banks are going after more clients with one another also hardened rivalry with tried and true banks. Client fulfillment is getting vitality because of extension of keeping money industry and imaginative items as per clients' necessities over the globe particularly in Pakistan. It is a movement of satisfying a need, craving, interest or desire. General fulfillment is the result of client's assessment of a set of encounters that are connected with the particular administration supplier (Westbrook, 1981). Client fulfillment is critical because of an expanded rivalry in saving money part (Bartell, 1993; Haron et al.1994). It is reasoned that client fulfillment improves the notoriety of the bank in the nature (Bontis, Booker and Serenko, 2007).

1.3-HISTORICAL BACKGROUND:

Housing building and finance trends are all towards South Asia and also towards African Sub Saharan division because of development and increasing the size of industry world over and to reduce poverty and bringing up prosperity, propensity to development in the regions. There is a major link between housing and growth and poverty development in housing finances of economic housing activity facilities formation.

In general economy industrial housing is a huge business of development and is highly cyclical changes over the world in costing the market value of the houses and the neighbourhood is the intentional issue for all people concerned. That can bring a change to life style of the society, families, households etc by regulating the programs of agencies and other builders and developers of construction business and it involves the complete process of continuous process of changing the society as a whole .

Housing choices for a families or an individual is dependable on the affordability factor which is more difficult significantly for lower income groups for spending on their expenditure towards housing because it is the basic need of life such as food, shelter, clothing and temporary housing or state level property. These type of people struggles throughout life to fulfill his or her basic needs and they sometimes become homeless even if they are employed. At communist level people are trying to give the housing facilities to poor people through charities, foundations and Land trust which only provide one unit to fulfill the requirement and are only for humanity services welfare plan of managing the control over poverty.

Humanity based workers who are providing the basic needs for human being for developing there selves in a more better way are constructing a low income group housing planned structures into the societies of there need. One should meet the monthly income requirement for paying off the debts and regular expenditure which is the basic need of all human being to spend on maintenance of their own shelter and it's the running expense.

Ownership requires allot of financial efforts which is not easy for every citizen in any country of this world. It is dependable on the purchasing power of an individual for becoming the home owner or starting the processing of buying home which is dependable on different market behaviors and power of purchasing of different human status.

The choice of the Shari Court has given the course to the banks, yet the genuine force lies in the hands of clients. This study will investigate the client's fulfillment with respect to the auto financing office of Meezan bank Ltd.

Center of this exploration might be on Isaiah. In Isaiah financing rights to utilize administrations of advantages are given by the lesser to resident. Property stays in the ownership of the lesser that is the manager and commitments with respect to proprietorship are borne by the lesser and commitments in regards to the utilization are borne by the renter.

The presence of two bank streams i.e. routine banks and Islamic banks represents some addresses about administration quality and clients' fulfillment in Pakistan. It is likewise critical to survey the impact of client fulfillment on bank execution. Islamic banks have opened new streets for acknowledgement of stores on premium free-premise and expand credit offices barring investment e.g. Qarz-e-Hasana and so forth. (Najajmabadi, 1991). It was observed that associations with bank staff are paramount criteria for choice of bank (Abratt and Russell, 1999).

1.4-JUSTIFICATION:

Research will distinguish the agreeableness of Islamic keeping money framework by the clients yet will especially concentrate on the house financing office. Exploration will likewise give the reply of these inquiries that why individuals incline toward house financing especially with the perspective of Meezan Bank Ltd and what are the primary motivational elements behind the determination criteria of house financing from Islamic banks.

1.5-RESEARCH PROBLEM:

Estimation of the customer selection criteria of house financing related to meezan bank limited.

1.6-RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

- 1-There is a positive relationship between cost and satisfaction.
- 2-There is a positive relationship between reputation and satisfaction.
- 3- There is positive correlation between service quality and satisfaction.
- 4-There is positive correlation between religiosity and satisfaction.

1.7-RESEARCH QUESTION:

How to estimate the satisfaction of customers regarding house finance of Meezan Bank Limited?

1.8- RESEARCH DESIGN:

Clients of Housing finance from Meezan Bank in Karachi are the aggregate population for this examination study. Accommodation examining (Non-likelihood Sampling) was utilized as an example method. Instrument utilized for exploration will be questionnaire of 100 to 120 sample size and as for gathering of information secondary sources are also being used. Exploration is quantitative in nature that is the reason SPSS was utilized and distinctive tests were directed.

1.9-RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

- 1- Objective of this research paper is to provide guidance who avail house finance facility from Meezan bank limited.
- 2- This paper will give an idea that which factor is most important factor for availability of housing finance facility from Meezan bank.
- 3- To identify the relationship among satisfaction, cost, reputation and service quality of Meezan bank limited.

2-LITERATURE REVIEW:

2.1-PRIMARY WELLSPRINGS OF SHARIA:

1. Sacred trust on Quran: The heavenly scripture of uncovered teachings which was sent to Muhammad sawby Almighty Allah.
2. Hadith: whatever Holy Prophet saw said and described identifying with the deeds of everyday life.
3. Sunnah: It implies frequent practices and conduct of Holy Prophet Saw throughout his whole life.
4. Ijma: agreement among Islamic ministers and researchers with respect to distinctive issues about which the Quran and Sunni don't give clear headings or eventually the Quran and Sunnah are quiet about those issues.
5. Qias: utilization of one's own judgment to give a feeling about an issue which is not depicted to in the blessed book known as Quran and Sharia.
6. Ijtihad: It implies aggregate insight is connected identified with the materialness of sharpie standards and standards which are not specified or even clarified in the Quran or in the Sharia.

2.2-STANDARDS OF ISLAMIC FINANCE:

1. Interest is not permitted and strictly denied in Islam
2. Credit based financing and managing is additionally disallowed.
3. Gharar is additionally not permitted and disallowed
4. Emphasis is given on transparent and full divulgence of every single data
5. Risk taking is not fitting or even it is stayed away from.
6. financing of for evil and socially flighty products and things are not permitted.
7. Concentration is more towards the danger offering rather than hazard taking.
8. Transactions including account must be finished in material term.
9. Justice and uniformity is given criticalness.
10. Exploitation of any gathering who is included in the transaction is not permitted.

2.3-ITEMS AND ADMINISTRATIONS OFFERED BY ISLAMIC FISCAL ORGANIZATIONS:

- Mudarabah: Capital is given on the premise of some allotment of (value offering premise) remembering in view the return for an offer of benefit.
- Musharakah: In this kind of financing, capital is given on the state of organization (value offering) and where reserve supplier and ambitious person both experience the business.
- Murabaha: In this financing option bank or budgetary organization buy the products and administration for the client and later one conveyed to client as indicated by the terms and conditions.
- Bai muajjall: In this mode of financing installment is made after a certain time of time.
- Bai Salam: In this mode of financing prepayment deal contracts of products and administrations are made.
- Istisna: In this mode of financing assembling contracts are taken into the attention to remunerate work in methodology and cases are fulfilled by the banks set up of clients.
- Ijarah: It the mode of lease financing in which working leases is advertised.
- Takaful: It is much the same as protection yet as indicated by the standards of Islam.
- Quard e Hassan: Interest free advance is given for a few purposes.

2.4-CONSUMER FINANCE:

Purchaser financing is the mode of financing whereby banks stretch out advance office to people for utilization. Obviously banks will be intrigued by financing the durables.

Said in (2003) that credit allowed to a single person for buying buyer merchandise as indicated by the need of clients is known as shopper financing. Auto financing, Home financing and individual advances are the samples.

Loaning through Master cards, particular credits, automobile advances, advances for durables and lodging money developed standards of purchaser account. They molded provincial request and giving technique by the keeping money division in truly inconspicuous ways. Buyer money has likewise brought social change through higher round of cash and unwinding of salary imperatives for acquiring especially among those working class fragments that were energetic to end up a piece of developing economy and quick to profit from monetary development. Without buyer fund being in the driving seat of the saving money area, countless would not have profited.

2.5-RIBA EXPLANATION:

They believe of Muslims on holy Quran gives the humanity a miraculous message for the expression of formulating Allah's that are perceived with some promises and commands. However Quran tells us the factual bayonet which is in clear teachings for the possibility of human language understanding and its real life implementation for developing a society based on human being welfare. The primary source is Quran and secondary is Hadith and Sunnah.

Riba means interest, which is disallowed in Islamic Law. Those who eat up usury won't. Those who accepting heading from their Lord, stop, should be absolved for the past; their case is for Allah (to judge); yet the individuals who rehash (the offense) are Companions of the Fire; they will withstand in that (eternity). Surah Name: AL Baqarah, Surah 2, Verse 2.

2.6-COST:

Plainly, giving money expenses money. Right when the costs are cut down, giving additions (Bekkers 2005d; Eckel & Grossman 2004; Eckel & Grossman 2003; Karlan 25 & List 2006). This is not to say that benevolence is energized by material increase to oneself: in light of the way that "promoters will always be better off not making a gift" (Sargeant & Jay 2004: 100). Examinations of hypothetical giving also indicate that demands for more amazing endowments are more unwilling to be respected (Andreoni & Miller 2002; Bekkers 2004). Developing the whole asked for may expand the entire gave if the aggregate asked for is not seen as compelling (Doob & Mclaughlin 1989). Regardless, one study found that a development for a "liberal obligation" instead of a particular total lessens the probability that a blessing will be made in course to-passage bargains (Weyant & Smith 1987). Desmet (1999) ran over a positive impact of advance all the more on standard gifts in a standard mail fight among sporadic suppliers, yet not among normal supporters. Additionally, higher blessings were balanced by an easier reaction rate. Relative disclosures are spoken to by Fraser, Hite and Sauer (1988). In a substitute study, a higher reference point obligation extended the aggregate gave, yet did not diminish the probability of making an insurance (Alpizar et al 2007).

2.7-REPUTATION:

Distinguishment may be given by persons who are not physically show. Fundamentally understanding that one's commitment is seen by others may be sufficient to impact individuals to give. In a study picking portions that impact giving all around a store raisers, Silverman et al. (1984)found that viewers were well on the best approach to give at the times when the names of ensuring suppliers were exhibited on the screen. Since more excellent get-togethers are usually more unacknowledged, it may be that rate and level of blessings abatement when social occasion sizes makes in bars and school classes (Wiesenthal et al 1983). Studies have constantly revealed a negative cooperation between the compass of social occasions and religious obligations (Davidson & Pyle 1994;hungerman 2005; Olson & Caddell 1994; Stonebraker 2003; Zaleski & Zech 1994; Zaleski et al 1994). While supporters regularly keep the nuts and bolts from securing social weight(polonsky et al 2002),studies have viewed that endowments are to a degree unequivocally identified with measures of social weight (Bekkers & Schuyt 2005; Mathur 1996; Pitts & Skelly 1984; Smith & Mcsweeney 2007).

2.8-SERVICE QUALITY:

Javier Reynoso et al. (1995) and Angur et al. (1999) exceptional that the open deliberation on SQ started in 1985 in the advertising writing and noteworthy commitments to the writing have additionally been made by those working in the field of operation administration and authoritative conduct. Accordingly, the exploration done in the territory of value in the keeping money industry has been found in a lot of people insightful diaries both scholastic and professional papers. Some of these studies from one perspective arrangement with definitions and outlines of SQ, measurements and estimations, and others completed by

professionals or scientists concentrate on the significance of SQ, utilitarian territories of the banks, appraisal and fruitful execution of current practice.

2.9-RELIGIOSITY:

Aydemir and Egilmez (2010), to investigate the relationship between religiosity and business morals, fight that a few researchers talk about whether religious convictions ought to be a suitable establishing for business morals. In their audit of writing, they experienced scientists who talked about a few suspicions, in particular: "religion and profound quality are synonymous"; business ethic has as of late ignored its religious conventions; instead of barring religion from business morals, business morals should think about religion as a solid ground; religions make profitable commitments to business morals; and, religions' qualities, standards, and practices give awareness of other's expectations, and direction to the businesses.(p. 72).

3-CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK:**INDEPENDENT VARIABLE****3.1-EXPLANATION OF CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK:****Cost:**

Valuation for cost and its benefits reflects the choices and preferences which have been selected by consumers based on their saving and money valuation and other financial analysis identical to its characteristics or scheduling the housing plan of payment for people.

Reputation:

For reputation ethical values, cultural values, integrity and the competency of the entity is the basic philosophy of the sector for developing managerial actions and operational styles of measurements.

Service quality challenges for sector:

Dealing up with the management expectation needs makes the internal control system more strong and beneficial towards people for the determination of continuous improvements of policies for the sector.

Financing policy and ownership:

When the buyer and the seller of a particular property agrees to purchase on the specific price with its owner agreed price to deposit it by the purchase, the particular bank will be the sole owner for registration of a financial policy between the two persons.

4. RESEARCH METHODOLOGIES:

EXPLORATION CONFIGURATION AND STRATEGY CLARIFY THE ACCOMPANYING COMPONENTS:

- Research hypothesis
- Operational definition of variables
- Data collection
- Discussion

4.1-RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS:

- 1-There is a positive relationship between cost and satisfaction.
- 2-There is a positive relationship between reputation and satisfaction
- 3- There is positive correlation between service quality and satisfaction.
- 4-There is positive correlation between religiosity and satisfaction.

4.2-OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF VARIABLES:

Autonomous Variable: Independent variable is the reason variable

1. **Religiosity:** Religiosity is an alternate component which assumes essential part in the choice of Islamic financing. The vast majority of the individuals who perform ceremonies customarily are more slanted towards the Islamic financing. Religiosity likewise incorporates support in the religious social occasions and linkage with the Islamic researchers and the individuals who take part in distinctive Islamic get-togethers and stay in contact with Islamic Scholars offer inclination to Islamic financing.

2. **Service Quality:** Quality of administration hails from two routes first from individuals and second from methodology.

3. **Sharia Compliance:** Shari consistence incorporates readiness and requisition of sharpie controls on the items and administrations of keeping money sectors. Role of Shari Advisor gets exceptionally imperative at the time of arrangement and provision of Shari guidelines in light of the fact that he guarantees that runs are as indicated by the instructing of Islam and no standard abuses the educating of Islam and Sunni. Clients additionally offer inclination to those Islamic banks which have prestigious Islamic Scholars connected with them and give direction at the time presentation of new items and congruity of existing items.

4. **Cost of financing:** Cost of financing is an alternate variable to be dissected at the time of selecting Islamic financing. There is contrast of feeling in regards to cost of financing one school of thought says that ease of financing is paramount that is the reason individuals favor Islamic financing and an alternate school of musings says expense of financing does not have any effect.

5. **Brand Name:** Brand name of Islamic bank is of key value and given inclination by clients. Notoriety and financing soundness of the bank are likewise taken into the attention at time of choice of bank.

Subordinate Variable: It is the conclusion variable. Subordinate variable is fulfillment of clients.

4.3-DATA COLLECTION:

Collection of data from all aspect is crucial for measuring the aspects of all type of research studies and invalid collected data will give an inaccurate results. Data collection method of my research will be measured through the questionnaire design based on liker scale which depends on our research design and methodology which is being adopted in overall research and its observations. Questionnaire results will be dependent on the following:

Without showing response of personal opinion.

Reading and analyzing the answers in a slow and gradual manner.

Will not answer any question other than respondents opinion.

Record the results as it is as the respondent answer.

5-DISCUSSION:

Customer Satisfaction:

Consumer loyalty is an advertising term that measures how items or administrations supplied by an organization meet or surpass a client's desire. Consumer loyalty is essential on the grounds that it gives advertisers and entrepreneurs with a metric that they can use to oversee and enhance their organizations. The level of fulfillment gave by the products or administrations of an organization as measured by the quantity of rehash clients

Cost:

Cost concept means that the amount where any asset is bought is to be written in the financial statement. The marked price is not to be written here but exact the amount in which the asset is bought should be written.

Reputation:

Reputation is a social element (an individual, a social gathering, an association) is a sentiment about that substance, regularly a consequence of social assessment on a set of criteria. It is imperative in business, instruction, online groups, and numerous different fields. Reputation may be considered as a part of way of life as characterized by others.

Activities performed by individual or organization which attempt to maintain or create a certain frame of mind regarding themselves in the public eye. Reputation management is the process of identifying what other people are saying or feeling about you or your business; and taking steps to ensure that the general consensus is in line with your goals. Many people and organizations use various forms of social media to monitor their reputation.

Service Quality: An assessment of how well a delivered service conforms to the client's expectations. Service business operators often assess the service quality provided to their customers in order to improve their service, to quickly identify problems, and to better assess

Religiosity:

Religiosity, in its broadest sense, is a thorough sociological term used to allude to the various parts of religious movement, commitment, and conviction (religious precept). An alternate term that would work similarly well, however less regularly utilized, is religiousness.

Religiosity is a term difficult to define (Fetzer Institute, 1999, Hackney and Sanders, 2003). All the people who have approached this domain have found it difficult to define religiosity when this concept is the subject of scientific research. Thus, there are multiple definitions and models. The majority of theorists say there is a distinction between religiosity and spirituality.

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